

What are Intrinsically disordered proteins (IDP)?

- Lack secondary or tertiary structure
- 1/3 of eukaryotes proteome
- Play a central role in cell regulation
- 70% of experimentally validated PTMs

AlphaFoldDB

Article

Highly accurate protein structure prediction for the human proteome

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03828-1>

Received: 11 May 2021

Accepted: 16 July 2021

Published online: 22 July 2021

Open access

Check for updates

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590 | Nature | Vol 596 | 26 August 2021

IDP Community organization and scope

- IDP Community proposal was accepted by the ELIXIR Head of Nodes on May 14th, 2019
- NGP-net COST Action (2015 - 2019) - Lead, Silvio Tosatto
- **Co-leads 2019-2023:** Zsuzsanna Dosztanyi (HU), Wim Vranken (BG), Damiano Piovesan (IT)

Wim Vranken
(ELIXIR Belgium)

Erdős Gábor Dániel
(ELIXIR Hungary)

Maria Cristina Aspromonte
(ELIXIR Italy)

Diana Battistella
(ELIXIR Italy)

Current co-leads

Goal: To drive the creation of high-quality tools and resources to support the identification, analysis and functional characterisation of IDPs

Community Success

Goal 1: Simplify IDP data access and dissemination

Goal 2: Drive the curation of IDP literature

Goal 3: Develop a centralised knowledgebase for IDP data

Goal 4: Integrate IDP data into ELIXIR Core Data Resources

Goal 5: Improve tools for IDP analysis

IDP Community organization and scope

Gender balance

13 nodes involved in the implementation studies so far

Links to **CDRs** and **IDP databases**

- *UniProtKB, InterPro, PDBe-KB, Gene Ontology*
- ***MobiDB, DisProt, PED, FuzDB, DIBS, MFIB, IDEAL, BMRB, PCDDDB, SASBDB, ELM***

The Community published
the whitepaper roadmap
on F1000 in 2019

OPINION ARTICLE

An intrinsically disordered proteins community for ELIXIR [version 1; peer review: 2 approved]

✉ Norman E. Davey¹, M. Madan Babu², Martin Blackledge³, Alan Bridge⁴, Salvador Capella-Gutierrez ¹⁵

IDP Community: implementation studies

- **2018-IDPs** - Integration and standardization of IDP data
 - **18 PMs** IT EBI CH HU IE
 - (1 year) **1 June 2018 - 31 May 2019**
- **2021-IDP** - Standardizing IDP data
 - **13 PMs** IT HU BE GR CZ, EMBL EBI ES CH CY^{*}, 8 ext.
 - (2 years) **1 January 2021 - 31 December 2022**
- **2021-IDPtools** - Improving IDP tools interoperability and integration into ELIXIR
 - **20 PMs** IT BE HU SP GR, DE CY, 2 ext.
 - (2 years) **1 June 2021 - 31 May 2023**

IDP Community - Network, interaction and visibility

- *ELIXIR bi-monthly Community meetings + AHM*
- *Scientific articles + reviews + protocols*

IDP Community Events

2018

- **IDP community kickoff meeting, Padova (17 June)**
- IDP-SIG ISMB/ECCB, Athene (8 Sept)

2019

- IDPfun All Hands Meeting 2019, Padova (3-7 June)
- AHM IDP workshop (17 June)
- Biohackathon, Paris (18-22 Nov)
- **IDP annual meeting, Padova (25-26 Nov)**

2020

- *IDP school, Brixen, Italy (27-31 Jan)*
- Biohackathon, Virtual (9-13 Nov)
- AHM Proteins workshop (IDP + 3D-Bioinfo + Proteomics) (8 June)

2021

- **IDP annual meeting, virtual (23-25 Feb)**
- *HUPO-PSI meeting, virtual (22-26 March)*

2022

- **IDP annual meeting , Brussels (24 - 27 January)**
 - *Intercommunity meeting (IDP, 3D-Bioinfo, proteomics)*
 - *Workshop - IDPcentral & IDP ontology*

2023

- HUPO-PSI meeting (WG), hybrid (17-18 April)
- COST Action ML₄NG Main Conference, Bratislava (4-7 July)
- **IDP community F2F/hybrid meeting, Bratislava (3-4 July)**

IDP community – Standardizing IDP data

- **MIADE** - Minimum Information About Disorder Experiment
- **HUPO-PSI format** - Adoption of MIADE in DisProt

- Sequence construct
- Experimental conditions
- Experimental components

Construct alteration

- Mutations
- PTM
- Tag
- Labels and dyes
- Non-standard amino acid

Experimental condition

- pH
- Temperature
- Pressure
- Oxidation-reduction potential

Experimental components

- interacting antibody
- interacting lipid
- interacting membrane
- interacting nucleic acid
- interacting protein
- interacting small molecule
- in-cell experiment

MIADE metadata guidelines: Minimum Information About a Disorder Experiment. Mészáros et al. – September 2023 - Nature Methods

DisProt in 2024: improving function annotation of intrinsically disordered proteins. Aspromonte MC, Nugnes Victoria et al., 2023 – NAR (Database issue)

DisProt Controlled vocabulary usage - MIADE

IDP community – Standardizing IDP data

- Controlled vocabulary integration: **Gene Ontology (GO)** and **Evidence and Conclusion Ontology (ECO)** terms
- DisProt GO terms propagated into UniProtKB
- PED ensembles available through the 3D-Beacons API

Evidence and Conclusion Ontology (ECO)

DisProt supports Evidence and Conclusion Ontology (ECO) ϕ to describe the technique or evidence used to assess the presence of disorder in an IDR/IDR or one of its associated disorder aspects

Explore ECO

Filter Search Clear

- author inference used in manual assertion (ECO:0005216 ϕ) A type of author inference that is used in a manual assertion.
- author statement used in manual assertion (ECO:0000302 ϕ) A type of author statement that is used in a manual assertion.
- combinatorial evidence used in manual assertion (ECO:0000244 ϕ) A type of combinatorial analysis that is used in a manual assertion.
- combinatorial experimental and curator inference evidence used in manual assertion (ECO:0007014 ϕ) A type of combinatorial evidence from curator knowledge and experimental evidence that is used in a manual assertion.
- curator inference used in manual assertion (ECO:0000305 ϕ) A type of curator inference that is used in a manual assertion.
- experimental evidence used in manual assertion (ECO:0000269 ϕ) A type of experimental evidence that is used in a manual assertion.

Namespace	Description
Molecular Function	Molecular-level activities performed by a given protein region
Biological Process	The larger processes accomplished by multiple molecular activities
Cellular component	The locations relative to cellular structures in which an IDRs/IDPs performs a function.

The Gene Ontology knowledgebase in 2023

GO Consortium - 2023 - Genetics

IDP community – Drive the curation of IDP literature

Guidelines implementation

Literature curation of IDP

Experimental characterisation of IDPs

OXFORD
ACADEMIC

DATABASE

The Journal of Biological Databases and Curation

Best practices for the manual curation of Intrinsically Disordered Proteins in DisProt

Federica Quaglia ^{1,2}, Anastasia Chasapi ³, Maria Victoria Nugnes ², Maria Cristina Aspromonte ², Emanuela Leonardi ², Damiano Piovesan ², Silvio C.E. Tosatto ^{2*}

Paper Submitted

IDP community – Drive the curation of IDP literature

Training platform and courses

- ELIXIR-SI eLearning platform
 - *Biocuration in DisProt (English & Spanish language)*
- Protocols

Biocuration in DisProt

UPDATED PROTOCOL | [Open Access](#) |

Exploring Manually Curated Annotations of Intrinsically Disordered Proteins with DisProt

This protocol is used in the article(s):

Federica Quaglia, András Hatos, Edoardo Salladini, Damiano Piovesan, Silvio C. E. Tosatto

Exploring predictions and annotations for intrinsically disordered proteins with MobiDB

Federica Quaglia^{1,2}, Maria Cristina Aspromonte^{1,2}, Alexander M. Monzon¹, Damiano Clementel¹, Damiano Piovesan¹ and Silvio C.E. Tosatto^{1,3}

Paper in preparation

IDP community – Drive the curation of IDP literature

Training platforms and courses

- TESS Webinars

DisProt and MobiDB databases

- Content of resources
- How to interpret entries
- How to navigate MobiDB and DisProt databases

ELIXIR Webinar

MobiDB
A database of protein disorder

7 September 2022 | 14:00 GMT

ELIXIR Webinar: An introduction to DisProt

Tue 16 August 2022, 14:00 BST

ELIXIR Webinar
Hosted by the ELIXIR Intrinsicly Disordered Proteins (IDP) Community

An introduction to DisProt

Intrinsicly Disordered Proteins

16 August 2022 | 15:00 CEST

Watch on YouTube

ELIXIR Webinar: Exploring structural and functional annotations of IDPs with DisProt

Tue 23 August 2022, 14:00 BST

ELIXIR Webinar
Hosted by the ELIXIR Intrinsicly Disordered Proteins (IDP) Community

Exploring structural and functional annotations of IDPs with DisProt

Intrinsicly Disordered Proteins

23 August 2022 | 15:00 CEST

Watch on YouTube

IDP community – Develop a centralised knowledge base for IDP data

- **Bioschemas** - Integrated service. Region annotation property in the Protein profile
- **IDPcentral** registry as use case of the Bioschemas strategic implementation study

The screenshot displays a web interface for defining a schema. The top section shows the schema definition for `hasSequenceAnnotation`, which is a property of type `SequenceAnnotation` (a subclass of `URL`) with a cardinality of `MANY`. The description is: "An annotation on the BioPolymerSequence associated with this BioChemEntity".

Below this, the JSON-LD representation of the schema is shown in a code editor. The JSON-LD includes the following fields:

```
1 {
2   "@context": "http://schema.org",
3   "@type": "Dataset",
4   "@id": "http://www.uniprot.org/uniparc",
5   "name": "UniProt Archive (UniParc)",
6   "description": "The UniProt Archive (UniParc) is a compr
7   "url": "http://www.uniprot.org/uniparc",
8   "identifier": "UniParc",
9   "keywords": "protein, protein sequence, archive",
10  "includedInDataCatalog": "http://www.uniprot.org",
11  "creator": {
12    "@type": "Organization",
13    "name": "UniProt Consortium"
14  },
15  "version": "2017-09",
16  "license": "Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivs",
17  "distribution": [
18    {
19      "@type": "CreativeWork",
20      "text": "A citation or reference to another creative work, such as another publication, web page, scholarly article, etc."
21    }
22  ]
23 }
```

The bottom section of the screenshot shows the definition for `Citation`, which is a subclass of `Text` with a cardinality of `MANY`. The description is: "A citation or reference to another creative work, such as another publication, web page, scholarly article, etc."

DisProt - intrinsic disorder evidence from the literature

Nucleic Acids Research, 2023, 1–8
<https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkad928>
Database issue

OXFORD

DisProt - intrinsic disorder evidence from the literature

 ☰

Welcome to **DisProt**, the database of intrinsically disordered proteins

Disordered regions are manually curated from literature. DisProt annotations cover both structural and functional aspects of disorder detected by specific experimental methods. [Read more about DisProt](#)

Search in DisProt

Organisms				Datasets			
1,119	210	74	171	NDDs-related proteins 312	Neglected tropical diseases proteins 101	Autophagy-related proteins 101	Cancer-related proteins 146
121	77	47	45	Viral proteins 210	Extracellular matrix proteins 66	Unicellular toxins and antitoxins 47	

- More than 100 curators → **APICURON**
- 7 thematic datasets based on organisms, diseases or biological processes of interest

DisProt - intrinsic disorder evidence from the literature

Scientific Paper

Biocurator

DisProt Entry

Minor errors:
Reviewer asks
for
modifications

Reviewer

It's ok:
Gets validated

It's wrong:
Gets
rejected

Release

A screenshot of the ELIXIR website. The top navigation bar includes 'ABOUT US', 'WHAT WE OFFER', 'HOW WE WORK', 'EVENTS', 'NEWS', and 'INTRANET'. The main content area is titled 'Biocuration Focus Group' and lists a steering committee with members: Federica Quaglia (ELIXIR-IT) - short bio - Chair, Valerie Wood (ELIXIR-UK) - short bio, Ulrike Wittig (ELIXIR-DE) - short bio, Sandra Orchard (EMBL-EBI) - short bio, Melissa Harrison (EMBL - EBI) - short bio, and Luana Licata (ELIXIR-IT) - short bio. A sidebar on the left lists focus groups: Biocuration, Cancer Data, EOCS, Environmental Impact, FAIR Training, and Health Data.

MobiDB - Mapping and combining IDP data

MobiDB's history

Extraction / processing of primary data
 Consensus / merging at the protein level

(Piovesan et al., *Nucleic Acids Research* 2023)

IDP community – Develop a centralised knowledge base for IDP data

- **MobiDB-lite** integration into **InterProScan**
- **Intercommunity** project

MobiDB

InterPro

UniProt

IDP community – Improve tools for IDP analysis

- **CAID** - Critical assessment of protein intrinsic disorder prediction (CAID 1 and CAID2)
- **CAID** prediction **portal** (<https://caid.idpcentral.org/challenge>)

ELIXIR IDP Community Review - September 2023

ELIXIR communities reviewed

Community name	Reviewers	Review Date
3D-BioInfo	Patricia Palagi, Irena Maus, Silvio Tosatto Tommi Nyronen (apologies)	22/05/2023
Microbial Biotechnology	Brane Leskošek, Ana Portugal Melo, Sushma Grellscheid, Riku Riski	24/05/2023
Intrinsically Disordered Proteins (IDP)	Jiri Vondrasek, Hedi Peterson, Mihail Anton, Rob Hooft	25/05/2023

- *“The IDP Community has been successful in bringing people together and doing work in the IDP field.”*
- *“...most of these achievements would not have happened if the Community had not existed, and thus it was important to have the Community structure to bring these scientists together.”*

- ❑ Update whitepaper with new goals for the Community
 - ❑ Involving more experimentalists in IDP Community
- Training courses specific for technique for the IDP interpretation